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Challenges Of Teaching In Early Childhood Care And Education Institutions In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

States that are desirous of sustainable and transformative developments invest in human capital development, that is provide education and in recent times, investment in human capital development has widened to include the foundational ages of citizens especially those within early childhood age of 0-5 years. Educational experience for citizens aged 0-5 years is called early childhood care and education. The growing awareness for providing early childhood care and education notwithstanding, care and educational experiences at this level faces monumental challenges that negatively affect learners and teachers who teach at this level of education. Theoretically guided by social constructivism and Maslow's hierarchy of needs and methodologically guided by the philosophical approach, this study discusses the challenges of teaching in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria. The paper identifies lack of direct and active participation by the government, sole participation in this level of education by private entrepreneurs whose sole motive for participation is profit maximization, lack of qualified teachers and mass exodus of the few who are qualified, lack of infrastructure and lack of professional developmental prospects for teacher as major challenges of teaching in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria. The paper recommends that government of Nigeria should actively and directly participate in providing early childhood care and education in Nigeria early childhood care and education should be compulsory and that the sight infrastructure should be provided among other recommendations.

Keywords: teaching, challenges, early childhood care and education in Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

One fact which permanently resonates across developed, developing and underdeveloped states and which developed, developing and underdeveloped state have equally come to wholeheartedly agree upon is the fact that the quality of general development which humanity experiences is strongly dependent on the quality of investments which states make in the area of human capital development and human capacity building. States that make investments in human capacity development and human capacity building a topmost priority in their national lives, national planning and national development policies reap multiple dividends from such national policy decisions and one can say very strongly that such states are guided in their approach to their national lives, national planning and national development by the awareness and recognition that human beings are the trigger and carriers of the genes (Eboh, 1998,

Nwaokugha & Agbarakwe, 2024) that flourish, blossom and translate into any form of development and correspondingly any state or society that is desirous of development in any of its ramifications must make investments in human capital development and human capacity building the centre and soul of its national policy decisions.

No doubt, every rational human being and every responsible state is desirous of growth and development and this natural urge and natural inclination for growth and development accounts for the high regard that is accorded to education, which is globally recognized as an institution and a social provision through which citizens and states can transcend frontiers, break through barriers and advance from levels of crude primitivity to levels of modern civility and technological sophistication that humanely add value to the quality of lives of citizens and the general improvement of the standards of living of humans across the globe. Because education is instrumental in guiding members of the society in the right directions including improving and advancing humans and their societies, most responsible states and societies make the provision of education a topmost priority (Shively, 2005) among all the social services that responsible states provide for their citizens and such responsible states have a plethora of justifications for their high regard for education.

Education is foundational in providing citizens with the necessary critical and creative potentials and resources for navigating situations and environments that human beings find themselves especially the possession of skills, dispositions and behaviours that can make them contribute positively to human developments but on the other hand to acquire and display behavioural attitudes that can make citizens to resist marginalization, deprivation and enslavement in the hands of the government. On the other hand, education is a ready-made instrument for stimulating and triggering social, political, economic, cultural and religious transformations and this, in all honesty points in the direction that education is a potential source and a springboard for bringing about positive changes in directions the government deems appropriate and desirable for the people and the state.

One dimension that has skyrocketed the global acknowledgement and recognition which people accord to education is the fact that education and its provision is a human right. What the global community recognizes as human rights enjoys a plethora of definitions and at the centre and heart of such definition is the recognition that a human right is that type of right which every human being, irrespective of sex, social status, religious affiliation, level of wealth in the possession and reach of the individual, political connections, background of the individual or level of developmental sophistication, civility or primitivity is expected to enjoy on ground of his or her being a human being. The global recognition of education as a human right derives impetus from the fact that education as a social provision is a foundational and fundamental necessity for the wellbeing and optimal functioning of the individual and the state, with the guiding operational principle for the intensification of its provision being that any individual that has been provided his rights to education has been empowered with skills and dispositions for adapting, navigating and responding to changes and challenges in an ever changing complex world, especially the imbibing and demonstration of positive changes that can bring about reformation and transformation of the individual and his state in directions that can enhance the individual's quality contributions to his personal survival and the sustainable development of his society and state. This is the reason or justification why individuals, parents and the state strive to make the provision of education to their sons, daughters and members of the state a topmost priority.

In fact, the provision of education to citizens and the citizens' effective exploration of the opportunity so far provided them is the foundation for national development in any of its configurations as individuals that have received education are the carriers of the genes that translate into development through their actions and activities. In recent times, there has been a growing awareness to deepen the provision of education so much that it becomes more inclusive and comprehensive so that no layer of the society is left behind and without access to education and this human capital development insight and revolution has expanded the education space so much that presently there are epical and phenomenal interests to consciously extend and expand educational provision to citizens in their earliest stages of life, precisely from the ages of 0 – 5. This drive for extended, expanded, inclusive and comprehensive investment in

human capital development in the education space and national development drive of states is called Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE).

The desire of states for quality development in the 21st century has positioned early childhood care and education, which is care and educational provision that is provided to the young ones from ages 0 – 5, in the case of some countries, for instance Nigeria, before they are officially admitted into the primary education institutions as a direction to go if the dreams and aspirations of states to get the best out of their investments in human capacity building and human capacity development and dreams of greatness are to be translated into reality. The guiding philosophy for this heightened and phenomenal attention to early childhood care and education aligns with the age long mantra of catch them young and it simply points in the direction that early investments in the child that translate into early development of the child or younger members of any state can bequeath to such younger ones the mission and responsibility to translate the visions of the founding fathers of such state into reality. It is a truth that cannot be doubted that any vision of growth, progress and development that any society or state dreams or aspires of can naturally be nursed in the minds of the founding fathers or elders of the society or state but cannot and may not be realized in totality by the founding fathers or elders themselves. The best the founding fathers or elders can do, which they have usually done is to shift the burden of the realization and actualization of their visions to the younger ones for translation into reality and translating and actualizing such visions into reality is only possible through quality investments in education, which must start at the level of early childhood care and education with focus on the care and education of the younger ones. Such remark above aligns with the remark dropped by Federico Mayor, a Past Director General of United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), who writes that “the world’s hope for the future rests with today’s young people and their readiness to take up the challenges of the coming century”.

Many leaders across states acknowledge and say in unison that their inability to adequately realize their developmental goals and objectives may be traced to their low commitment and neglect of quality investments in early childhood care and education, a development they are presently revisiting with the intention to robustly harness and receptively explore potentials that come with investments in the sector and in line with the acknowledgement of the above, scholars strongly make case for early childhood care and education through recognizing many potential benefits that come with providing early childhood care and education experiences and such benefits that come with providing early childhood care and education range from the ability of the younger ones to develop receptive dispositions towards learning and education and internalizing behaviors that are supportive of robust and vibrant academic pursuits and achievements (Nwaokugha & Agbarakwe 2024). Provision of early childhood care and education is a source of hope and relief for young ones who live in poverty, denial, marginalization and deprivation and by extension a conscious and systematic measure to take a state and her people to the next level of positive development. In fact, Mahadewi (2024:1) says it all when he writes that South African government recognizes “the potentials of early childhood care and education to elevate poverty and inequality”. What the above can be pointing hand to is that prioritizing the provision of early childhood care and education to the citizens of a state is a fundamental and necessary entry points for laying strong and formidable foundations that can translate into making welfare and social justice mechanisms, norms and practices part and parcel of the official social, economic and political policies of the state especially those that can lead to a more equal, orderly, harmonious, development and justice conscious society. It is very obvious that any state that prioritizes the provision of early childhood care and education in its educational structure has consciously instituted a legacy as well as set up a trajectory for predicting and determining what becomes of the individual and the state in the near future.

A more robust, inclusive and comprehensive benefit of early childhood care and education is provided by Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:60) when they write that:

Early childhood care and education institutions are noted globally for their drives in developing the social, emotional cognitive developments of learners as well as promoting in learners' behavioral attitudes that stimulate in them the curiosity for receptive embrace of formal primary education, developments that are solid foundations for human capacity building and human capacity development of states in the future.

With the benefits of providing early childhood care and education as outlined above, it is possible any one with the least or lowest level of critical and analytic thinking may logically come to the conclusion that all the benefits which are associated with early childhood care and education can manifestly and latently come to fruition through the efforts of the teacher, courtesy of his teaching approaches and procedures in early childhood care and education institutions. Indeed, teaching and the teacher particularly in decent teaching and learning environments where infrastructure is in adequate supply and teachers' welfare are guaranteed are fundamental in bringing out and positioning to eminent prominence all the developmental trajectories that early childhood care and education brings to light. In fact, to say the truth, the global acknowledgement of the fact that the future and developmental trajectories of the state is strongly hinged on the systematic and conscious move of the state to effectively educate her younger ones can be conscious appeal in the form of urging stakeholders in early childhood care and education to correspond the importance of the sector with the provision of infrastructure, decent working environment, welfare services for staff or for short accord the sector all the relevant attention due to it so that everything required for greater productivity will be available. However, be this as it may, there is a worrisome trend and a course for concern: teaching in early childhood care and education institutions is plagued with challenges so visible that Mahadewi (2024:1) write that "ECCE personnel encounter challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, limited professional development opportunities and insufficient resources which adversely affect their ability to deliver quality education and care". In the same orgy of graphic portrayal of challenges in the early childhood care and education sector, Kim, Brand and Zeltzer (2024) identify challenges that early childhood care and education faces in the United States to include "low wages, lack of benefits and high turn over rate, which are significant factors that impact the professional lives of the workforce in early childhood care and education institutions. That these challenges exist in high profile and developed countries may be revealing that early childhood care and education in developing and under developed countries may be worse hit by challenges which in totality may have been compromising the quality of early childhood care and education institutions in such areas and corresponding limiting the citizens from the benefits of such foundational and transformative intervention in education. Again, that educational provisions at this foundational and transformative intervention stage suffer these phenomenal deficits maybe a pointer to serious issues that have potentials to signal challenges, dangers, helplessness, hopelessness and powerlessness for teachers who teach at this level of education.

This study aims at highlighting the challenges which teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria face, identify the sources of such challenges, list why such challenges may continue to plague the early childhood care and education sector as well as profer solutions on how to address such challenges. The study in all honesty can be significant in a number of ways. The study can create awareness on the existence of such challenges in the early childhood care and education segment of our educational institution. Our ability to identify and discuss such challenges can illuminate lights into ways of addressing and resolving such challenges. In a way, our efforts can align with the age long mantra that problems identified are half solved and correspondingly contribute meaningfully to the growth and expansion of knowledge in the field of early childhood care and education in particular and teaching, teacher education and general advocacy for improving issues in teaching and early childhood care and education.

Two theoretical frameworks namely social constructivism, which is also called social constructionism and Maslow's hierarchy of needs guided the study. Social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction invokes a meaning that revolves around the thesis that human beings construct, generate,

establish and build knowledge from their daily or day to day experiences and interactions with fellow human beings in any environment or institution they find themselves, a development which suggests that no knowledge is ready made but that human beings strive, crave and creatively venture into creating knowledge through God-endowed innate creative and critical thinking skills of man. What this reveals is that social constructivism aligns harmoniously with qualitative research paradigms and according to Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:167), is a trigger and a ready-made instrument in the hands of scholars who are committed to breaking new frontiers of knowledge, who are committed to solving and responding to the demands of change, who are desirous of collaborating with others and more importantly who are desirous of exploring and exhibiting the highest forms of critical and creative thinking.

Maslow's hierarchy of needs has been influential and correspondingly contributed immensely in the world of knowledge across the world and will continue to be explored in academic discussions across many academic disciplines. Maslow's hierarchy of need is unique in influencing, predicting and determining how the ability of the individual to meet up his or her basic fundamental physiological needs or the ability of a state to provide the basic necessities for the survival of her citizens can be a trigger and a motivating force for the individual or citizens to aspire for greater achievements and consequently dream towards their self-actualization in any field of their chosen endeavours. What is at the heart of Maslow's hierarchy of needs especially at the early childhood care and education level is the recognition that all things being equal, a critical factor in the line of development of any individual is the ability of the individual to first of all fulfill every basic deficiency that may exist in his or her life before any conscious aspiration that may be targeted at the development of cognitive and aesthetic skills that are triggers for self-actualization can become successful.

Early childhood care and education is a flashpoint in discussions where focus is on determining whether basic deficiency needs of individuals have been met so as to challenge the individual to aspire for cognitive and aesthetic developments that are necessary conditions for self-actualization. Anyone who is familiar with developments at this foundational, fundamental and critical stage in the individuals drive for educational pursuit especially in developing countries can quickly come to the conclusion that basic requirements for efficient and effective development of the younger ones to effectively learn or trigger teachers to become more committed and dedicated so as to increase their productivity are terribly and disastrously not available. The poor state of infrastructure in early childhood care and education institutions is graphically highlighted by Mahadewi (2024:4), when he writes that "the persistent lack of resources and unmet basic needs further compounds children's challenges in reaching their full developmental potential, compounding the predicaments of learners is the fact that teachers who teach at this level of education hardly see any ray of hope in terms of professional developmental prospects or improvements in their welfare, developments that consistently remove all aura of job satisfaction from them.

Here lies the fact in the use of Maslow's hierarchy of needs as a theoretical framework for a study on early childhood care and education and that fact is simple, namely, the inability of younger ones or products of early childhood care and education institutions to academically and cognitively fulfill all the basic learning requirements expected of them at the early childhood care and education level due to lack of infrastructure, lack of job satisfaction, resources, lack of expertise in teaching strategies and government's lackadaisical attitudes cannot and will not transition or navigate them out of the base or the physiological and psychological levels of Maslow's hierarchy of needs, a sad development that has potentials that are capable of preventing and limiting learners from launching themselves to the level of self-actualization and achievement of their full potentials and this has serious implications for national development especially for those states that are serious and desirous of human capacity building and national development.

The importance of social constructivism for this study is its ability to create the right awareness and insights that human beings create knowledge through their experiences and interactions with fellow human beings and correspondingly aligns with the position maintained by Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:62), who make case that social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction must

prioritize active engagement and active participation of persons or learners in the knowledge industry who are curious and desirous of generating and expanding the frontiers of knowledge while the relevance of Maslow's hierarchy of needs for this study is on its emphasis on the need of any individual or state that is desirous or determined to develop its human resources and human capacity development through early childhood care and education to strive and endeavour to meet up all the basic needs that can lead to the fulfilment and actualization of all the predetermined dreams, without which all such dreams, visions and efforts will be attempts in futility.

Methodologically, the researchers adopt the philosophical research design which is also called qualitative research design in carrying out this study. In recent times, philosophical or qualitative research design has gained wide spread attention more than other research paradigms and what accounts for this is its numerous adaptable features and characteristics which allow scholars and researchers to freely communicate and express their ideas. Angadi (2019:37) acknowledges such vast features and characteristics of philosophical or qualitative research paradigm when he writes that philosophical or qualitative research methodology heavily relies on the collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over an extended period in a naturalistic setting to gain insights not possible using other types of research methodology. The use of the philosophical research methodology allows a scholar or a researcher to creatively and robustly build abstractions from his extensive narrative data and basically the researcher is instrumentally the basic instrument for data collection where the researcher strictly and religiously makes semantic clarity (meaning) and rigours of thought basic tools for his epistemological and philosophical expedition.

From another perspective, Ishtiaq and Naz (2024:10) describe philosophical or qualitative research methodology especially in the field of education as:

Often exploratory, aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational settings. Qualitative research in education involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data such as interviews, observations, case studies and document analysis. The aim is to generate in-depth insights, explore meanings and understanding the underlying processes that shape educational phenomena

What may be called an inclusive and comprehensive feature of philosophical or qualitative research is provided by Nwaokugha and Danladi (2016) when they write that philosophical or qualitative research methodology incorporates speculation, analysis and prescription. Speculation as a way of carrying out philosophical studies is not a new comer in the world of knowledge as it has been there in the past and in the words of Nwaokugha and Nwoagu (2024:63) has been reinvented in new forms in the present age where there is epical, monumental and phenomenal explosion in knowledge.

The overarching and all-embracing nature of speculation can be attested to in this remark by Gare (2020), who writes that speculation is primordial to all experience and thinking and Currie (2021), who writes that speculation is critical for successful science, a pointer that speculation can be applied across all areas of knowledge. What lends credence to the importance of speculation in the pursuit of knowledge is the exponential attention that is given to it by scholars and researchers. In fact, Nwaokugha and Agbarakwe (2024:253), say it all when they write that speculation is interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary, a point they demonstrated when they write that the term can be applied in philosophy and its applied disciplines, social sciences and natural sciences. In acknowledgement of the interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary outlooks or usage of speculation, Swedberg (2021:46), writes that speculation has two basic meaning namely speculation refers to risky but potentially very profitable economic activity and it also refers to the making of conjectures without firm evidence. The above chameleonic nature of the term according to Nwaokugha and Agbarakwe (2024:253), reveals that one meaning of speculation in one context or discipline may not be the meaning of the same term in another context or discipline and on the basis of this, speculation enjoys a robust scholarly attention in the form of having different destinations from different scholars and researchers. In this study, we shall confine ourselves to the second meaning of speculation as indicated above.

Aminigo (1999) and Agulanna (2011) defines speculation as an attempt to find logical coherence in an entire realm of thought. According to Odour (2010:97), to speculate is to wonder, conjecture, guess and to hypothesize. In the words of Huang, Xie and Chen (2021:1), speculation and speculative thinking invokes a meaning that revolves around thinking about past and future possibilities, which includes counterfactual thinking, pre-factual thinking and other types of thinking. Speculation in practice maintains logical and epistemological trajectories where scholars and researchers who are receptively disposed to using it coherently build up their ideas and systematically show how one idea is logically linked to the other in the entire build up of the whole ideas and this logical sequence of building up ideas corresponds to what Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:4) call a sense of logical unity, logical coherence and logical clarity about a presentation that is the subject matter of a philosophical discourse.

The overriding importance of speculation and speculative thinking in knowledge construction is hinged on the fact that speculation and speculative thinking is at the centre of conscious epistemological drives, actions and initiatives that target providing insights on how practices and behaviours can be improved upon for greater productivity in the future. This simply means that speculation and speculative thinking is the epistemological navigating compass and guide for reforms, transformation and innovations (Nwaokugha & Nwaogu, 2024:63) in the affairs of man and his institutions. Such forward looking outlooks that are inherent in speculation and speculative thinking may have prompted Taggart (2012) into observing that speculation and speculative thinking aims at providing man and his institutions with high order consolation, a kind of philosophy of action for shaping and influencing people's general outlook to life and correspondingly speculation and speculative thinking functions as a provocateur. In fact, speculation drives in man the curiosity to know especially the curiosity to break epistemological frontiers and barriers on any subject matter that is the focus of the speculation and this calls to mind the age long saying that people speculate in order to know the true nature of reality. On the basis of the above observation, all realities that lack fix or universal answers are the most receptive and attractive topics to speculation and this is also why metaphysical and axiological topics namely aesthetics ethics, social and political philosophy cannot escape speculation and speculative thinking. Speculation and speculative thinking are heavily dependent on logic and on one hand and effective and convincing manipulation and use of language on the other.

Analysis as a methodology of philosophical or qualitative research focuses on critical and detailed examination of words, terms, concepts and propositions so as to establish meanings that are associated with such words, terms, concepts and propositions and the reason why meaning of words, terms, concepts and propositions are a focal flash point in analysis is that words terms, concepts and propositions are the vehicles for communicating ideas on one hand and are signals for driving meanings on the other. On the basis of this, analysis prioritizes clarification of ambiguities, contradictions, absurdities and the encouragement or promotion of precision in the use of words, terms, and concepts in communication or interaction with people. Why precision is a topmost priority in analysis is the recognition by specialists in analysis that virtually all issues bordering on crises, misunderstandings and conflicts that have stagnated man and his development owe their roots to miscommunication, faulty communication or faulty use of words, terms, and concepts. It then follows that when analysis is properly done, it helps to reduce the occurrence of conflicts, helps in the resolution of conflict and disagreements and misunderstanding, helps in laying foundations for the promotion of peace, harmonious and cooperative living as well as the stimulation of sustainable practices for development. In short Nwaokugha (2021:160) highlights the numerous benefits the use of analysis as a philosophical research methodology can trigger in a society when he writes that:

The advantages of analysis are that through it, meanings are clarified and ambiguities are resolved, and this clarification and resolution of ambiguities helps members of the society to amiably address, resolve and bring to the barest minimum the occurrence of conflicts, misunderstandings, disagreements, violent confrontations that make peace elusive by threatening harmonious coexistence and progressive development of the society.

How to go about analysis according to Nwaokugha and Danladi (2016:421) is one in which the analyst “starts by breaking down his subject matter into smaller units that constitute it and at the same time shows how all are related in attaining a specific objective”. Analysis is of two types namely linguistic and conceptual analysis. Any analysis that focuses on ascertaining whether the meaning that is ascribed to a sentence is really what that sentence is all about is linguistic analysis while conceptual analysis is any analysis that focuses on establishing if the meaning that is ascribed to a concept, a word, or a term represents what that concept, word or term stands for. Logic and language are fundamental in any meaningful analysis.

Prescription in the context of methodology for carrying out philosophical studies or researches invokes a meaning that revolves around the ability of a researcher or a scholar to consciously and systematically establish standards for making prescriptive value judgments or lay foundations upon which a scholar or a researcher can establish standards for judging values. It is natural and of utmost importance for any study that is worth the name to focus on solving and resolving one problem or the other and the various autonomous and systematic steps identified and listed out by a scholar or a researcher for solving and resolving such identified problems qualify as prescription. This is why Oduor (2010:97) is on point when he writes that “to prescribe is to recommend or set down as a rule or a guide” and Nwaokugha (2021:102) is more direct when he says that prescription as a philosophical research methodology;

Is achieved in research in the form of a researcher making autonomous value statements on how an issue that has been the focus or subject matter of a philosophical discussion can be solved so that all the wrongs noticed in the course of the discussion can be harmoniously addressed. In this way, suggestions and recommendations in researches and other forms of writing fall within the frame of reference of prescription.

We can highlight the importance of prescription in philosophical research in particular and the world of knowledge generally by pointing out that there are scholars and disciplines that prescription is at the heart of their scholarship and correspondingly prescription provides them sustainable space and platform to maximally serve humanity. Scholars and disciplines whose epistemological areas of investigation fall within the realms of axiology, social philosophy, aesthetics, ethics and political philosophy must make prescription an article of faith for success in their academic endeavours.

There are many justifications why philosophical or qualitative research methodology has become a destination of choice for scholars and researchers and why it is necessary for this particular study. Philosophical or qualitative research methodology is instrumental in inspiring ground breaking breakthroughs across disciplines especially in the twenty first century (Nwaokugha & Nwaogu, 2024) and this is due to its potentials and receptivity to raising researchers’ and scholars’ curiosity for investigating and breaking new frontiers of knowledge, a development which Nwaokugha and Ihuoma (2019:277) highlight when they write that philosophical or qualitative research methodology boosts;

The confidence level of researchers as researchers see every challenge in any academic discipline as solvable and resolvable. In fact, philosophical research method of enquiry stimulates in researchers the desire to critically and continuously try out new academic options that can result in phenomenal improvement of scholars and the breaking of new frontiers of knowledge.

A more detailed, inclusive and comprehensive benefits of philosophical or qualitative research methodology is provided by Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:168) when they write that:

The philosophical research methodology is credited with widening scholars and researchers investigative skills, promotes collaboration that results in the breaking of new frontiers of knowledge as through it researchers and scholars summon up courage to investigate areas of knowledge which ordinarily are unmentionable and un-contemplatable and finally as the use of the philosophical research methodology engineers epistemological revolution that triggers phenomenal breakthroughs in knowledge, man’s quality of life receives quality

improvements through opening of more opportunities for man to benefit from his investments in research and education.

What has become the norm with studies that adopt the philosophical or qualitative research methodology is to vividly present and critically discuss key term(s) or concept(s) that are the focus of the studies or investigation and to this we now turn.

Early Childhood Care and Education

Across the globe, education and its provision receives phenomenal attention so much that it is always at the centre of politics, policy, development of plans by states, centre of regional, international and global deliberations as well as focus of empowerment decisions of leaders and their states and one development that almost regularly accompanies this attitude to education is that new trends, new ways of instruction, introduction of innovations and expansion of the educational space are constantly introduced into the education industry that principally makes access to education a top-most priority. Prior to this time, access to education was centred on learners in the primary, secondary and tertiary levels of education and what may have influenced this or may be responsible for this may be the recognition and acknowledgement of states of the roles of human capital development and human capacity building in the development of states. It is not to be doubted that human beings are the carriers of the genes that translate into development, a realization that suggests that the quality of development any state can boast of depends on the quality of investments such state make in its citizens especially in younger ones.

The natural endowment of man which principally manifests in man's ability to indulge in rational, critical and creative thinking equips him with the capacity and capability to evaluate his actions and practices especially in the education industry. The result of this self-evaluation or self-correction mechanism has been man's acknowledgement that education has not optimally performed in terms of influencing development in all its ramifications and configurations and the source of this deficit and deficiency in education is traced to the foundation of those in the education system. The awareness that the foundation of the product of the education system is infested by terrible deficits and deficiencies has challenged stakeholders especially in education to resort or appeal to the inherent self-correction mechanism and dynamics in education, and the step has been conscious state policy that makes the provision of learning and educational experiences to learners prior to learners' enrolment into formal educational system notably the primary school and providing learning and educational experiences to learners prior to learners' admission or enrolment into formal education institution goes by the name early childhood care and education (ECCE).

Leaders in states and education stakeholders acknowledge the fact that sound foundations for learners or precisely catching learners young through orienting them to the values and potentials of education and raising their curiosity for educational pursuits early in life holds the key to unlocking all human potentials and repositioning states for genuine national development. In fact, the realization across states of how early childhood care and education can reposition states and turn the fortunes of the states around for the better has generated considerable attention to early childhood care and education and what has resulted out of this has been different policy declarations and statements from different states on how to practically and realistically implement policies and explore opportunities that come with providing education to learners at this level of their development. Following this, different states have different policy statements and declarations or mandates concerning early childhood care and education. It has to be noted that although there is a global recognition to start the provision of education to learners early in life, individual states decide the specific age bracket to label or designate as their own early childhood care and education period and following this caveat, some states peg their early childhood care and education at 0-5 years, with the earlier segments 0-3 years of age devoted to care and the rest for rudimentary education, some states peg theirs from birth to eight years (UNESCO, 2017), (Kim, Brand & Zeltzer, 2024) and from birth to nine years of age (Kuhne & Fakie, 2019) respectively. Such developments may not be a surprise because no two states according to Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:66) has a uniform practice in terms of how their early childhood care and education arrangements or services can be provided as the level of developmental sophistication or otherwise of each state, the level of commitment of individual state to

welfare, economic buoyancy and political stability, commitment to human capital development and human capacity building, commitment to social justice programmes and initiatives, all combine to determine, shape and influence the dispositions of states towards the provision of early childhood care and education to their citizens. In all of the states, care, which is the surveillance of the adult over the younger person comes first before education and there are noticeable differences in the quality of care and educational provision at this level across states. In the same way, there are common threads that run through all learning and educational experiences at this level namely early childhood care and education irrespective of state is a conglomerate of custodial surveillance and basic rudimentary instructional activities and practices that take place simultaneously (Nwaokugha, 2016), which may be provided to the younger ones at home or in centres before their admission into primary educational institutions.

States generally agree in their policy directions and mandates that early childhood care and education is beneficial and aims to promote the physical, cognitive, social, emotional, and language development of children (Ghosh, 2021, Mahadewi, 2024). Udayanga (2024:2) is more inclusive and comprehensive in his discussion of the benefits of early childhood care and education as he writes that quality early childhood care and education programmes provide essential skills, support cognitive development and enhance social integration as well as helps to empower children in vulnerable communities, offering a path way to break the circle of poverty and build a stronger, more resilient society, where justice and equality can become norms. The benefits of providing early childhood care and education is not limited to children alone. Early childhood care and education institutions provide safe environment or offer custody responsibilities for children so as to enable their parents to continuously attend to the other of their social and economic responsibilities. This points in the direction that early childhood care and education institutions provide families ample opportunities to actively go about their normal business and daily work schedules without the inconveniences that come with the presence of younger ones in the family. By implication, early childhood care and education creates employments for members of the society and helps to reduce unemployment. Early childhood care and education triggers the cognitive curiosity of its products as it has been established that learners who passed through early childhood care and education institutions perform exceptionally better morally and academically and this helps to drastically reduce costs associated with remedial education. In short early childhood care and education gives the young ones a vision and a future, as through it, any responsible state can sustainably launch and initiate durable and long-lasting welfare and social justice programmes that can announce the state at the global stage.

In addition to all the benefits that humanity stands to gain from providing and participating in early childhood care and education, one benefit strongly stands out; conscious provision of early childhood care and education triggers in the younger ones curiosity and readiness for formal educational activities at the primary school level (Nwaokugha & Nwaogu, 2024), implying that investments in the young ones at the early childhood care and education level and constitutionally recognizing early childhood care and education level is the proper way to go in term of kick-nstarting and placing the younger ones on the right track that can enable them do well both in their educational pursuits and survival in the future and laying sustainable foundations for the national development of the state.

Teaching

One human activity and profession that is key in discussions that border on human capital development, human capacity building and by extension national development of state is teaching, which Okoh (2003:71) define as:

The conscious and deliberate effort by a mature or experienced person to impart information, knowledge, skills and so on, to an immature or less experienced person with the intention that the latter will learn or come to believe what is taught on good grounds.

What is done in teaching and what the society achieves through teaching is so phenomenal that teaching enjoys an appreciable level of recognition among all the social services that responsible states provide for their citizens and why this is so is that effective and meaningful teaching is fundamentally responsible for the reformation and transformation of the learner, who is usually inexperienced and immature and who,

by divine providence needs to be adequately protected, socialized, sensitized and guided so that he develops along trajectories where he becomes useful to himself and the society where he belongs. This means that effective and meaningful teaching brings about reformation, transformation and change of the learner from crude to refined, bad to good behaviours through appropriately guiding and developing the learner's sense of value and autonomous reasoning so that the learner can on his own make right choices and take right decisions that can produce the best results both for himself and the larger society.

By these provisions and prescriptions, teaching is a unique, conscious, intentional and deliberate activity in the sense that it is one fundamental channel for realizing and actually the ideals of education through systematically and consciously initiated pedagogical actions that are also intended to stimulate, induce and trigger learning by a professionally mature and experienced person, who is determined to impart knowledge, skills, values and information that are considered worthwhile to less experienced persons who have voluntarily chosen to submit themselves to the guidance of the experienced person. The emphasis and preoccupation of teaching on experiences or values that are worthwhile is the sole reason why globally teaching is regarded as a moral enterprise. In practice, teaching is effectively realized through a process of communication. Put slightly different, teaching revolves around a triadic communication process between a teacher, a subject matter and a learner or learners and for teaching to be effective and successful, there must be a methodology through which the teacher communicates the subject matter to the learner(s). Any good teaching must incorporate more than one methodology and any methodology to be used according to Okoh (2003:73) must (a) respect the integrity of the learner (b) must be democratic (c) must be characterized by appeal to rationality and development of independent judgement in the learner (d) must stimulate the learner to learn and provide guidance so that the learner can be innovative (e) must be open ended, that is, allows room for further development.

The above expositions reveal that teaching must come to function through the efforts of somebody who creates the necessary environmental conditions that facilitate teaching and learning and that person is the teacher. A teacher according to Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:67)

Is a person who enrolled and received professional education in a teacher education institution or other designated centres that are affiliated to teacher education institutions and whose quality of professional education enables him or her after the completion of the teacher education programme to function at multiple levels such as providing pedagogical instructions that target stimulating in learners the ability and capacity to learn, knowledge that enables him or her to serve as a bridge builder between learners and learners, between learners and parents, between educational institutions and other institutions in the state and above all professionally possessing good knowledge of a subject matter or matters, good knowledge of the learner, the society as well as knowledge of how to methodologically manipulate the environment to stimulate in learners the curiosity, capacity, capability and enthusiasm to learn.

The importance of the teacher in any meaningful and effective teaching learning process and national development of states is so phenomenal that scholars and researchers acknowledge that the quality and personality of the teacher "in the education system of a state is the most important factor upon which the quality and standard of education and correspondingly the quality of development in any state can be judged" (Nwaokugha & Nwaogu, 2024:68). The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) confirms the above high profile of the teacher when it writes that "no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers"

With such high regard for the teacher in human capacity building, human capital development and national development of the Nigerian state, it can be taken to mean that the Nigerian state may accord or must accord high regard to the teacher across the various levels teachers teach so much that teachers may not experience challenges especially on the line of their duties. The high regard that is accorded to teaching does not actually correspond with what prevails in practice, meaning that the reality of things in the education industry or teaching profession especially as it concerns teaching and the teacher

particularly in Nigeria is one where policy summersault, political maneuvering and manipulations, lack of infrastructure for teaching and learning, poor conditions of service, poor salaries, low incentives and lip service are the cardinal operational paradigms that define teaching and the teacher, developments that have made the prevalence of mainly negative emotions- anger, frustration, anxiety, sadness, intrusion and uncertainty (Kelchtermans, 1996), normal day to day affairs in the management, administration and operations of educational institutions in Nigeria.

Positive and negative emotions exist in teaching, however, Nwaokugha (2014:18) acknowledges that teachers in Nigeria experience mainly negative emotions, which according to him spring from issues of poor conditions of service and official neglect of incentives for the teacher and terrible state of infrastructure in the education industry. These have become so permanent and so entrenched so much that attempts at addressing them constantly backfire in the form of stifling teachers enthusiasm and creativity (Frymier, 1989) but at the same time multiply challenges in the education industry in Nigeria. True, no level of education in Nigeria is exempted from the plethora of challenges in teaching and learning but the focus of this study, which the next section of the study addresses is challenges of teaching of teaching in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria.

Challenges of teaching in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria

One common denominator that is prevalent in most developing and under developed states is the underfunding of educational institutions, which consequently has made challenges a common trend that the educational institutions must coexist with. However, there is a level of educational provision where challenges do not respect the level of developmental sophistication of states, implying that challenges phenomenally exist at this level of education. This level of education where challenges phenomenally exist irrespective of developmental sophistication of states, is early childhood care and education and such challenges have direct and indirect implications for teaching, learning and teachers who teach at this fundamental and foundational level of the educational system. Though a universal trend for teachers, teachers who teach in early childhood care and education centres in Nigeria go through phenomenal and excruciating challenges.

Challenges of teaching in early childhood care and education centres in Nigeria and the challenges teachers who teach in early childhood care and education centres in Nigeria face derive from different sources. Nigeria as a country has a provision in its education policy where the provision of education at this critical and foundational stage in the citizens' quest and pursuit of education is the exclusive reserve of the private sector or private investors. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004:11) testifies to this when it writes that:

The responsibilities of government for pre-primary education shall be to promote the training of qualified pre-primary school teachers in adequate number, contribute to the development of suitable curriculum, supervise and control the quality of such institutions and establish pre-primary sections in existing public schools.

Anyone who has the least ability to think critically and analytically cannot struggle to arrive at the fact that there may be the possibility of infrastructural deficiency or decay and that teachers in Nigeria whose areas of specialization are early childhood care and education are automatically condemned to apply for jobs or to only work all through their lives for private establishments where job security and enhanced conditions of service can permanently and everlastingly be a distance dream. In fact, teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria are at the mercy of entrepreneurs whose objectives are to explore and harness the already available market that promises huge returns on investment, which the education industry guarantees investors especially at the early childhood care and education level and not an adventure that is targeted at rescuing the education system in the form of assisting the state or humanity to render a critical service. Scholars who argue that the involvement of the private investors in education particularly early childhood care and education are Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:69), and they maintain that the involvement of the private investors in early childhood

care and education “is a business outfit and a capitalistic adventure for profit and exploitation of the people” where the major beneficiaries are the investors or the entrepreneurs and not the teachers.

Facing reality on the part of the private investors in terms of providing the right infrastructure, professional development, training, paying living wage and providing the right environment that can stimulate creativity or optimal performance and correspondingly promote productivity on the part of the teachers has been a cardinal challenge that undermines the activity, creativity, productivity, responsiveness and responsibility of teachers in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria. In fact, the absence of infrastructure, staff development opportunities and programmes, provision of living wage and conducive environment for teaching and learning have been noted by different scholars as principal challenges in early childhood care and education in Nigeria that undermine teachers’ ability to function effectively and productively. In Nigeria as in other developing countries of the world, teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions encounter challenges, including what Mahadewi (2024:1) calls inadequate infrastructure, limited professional development opportunities and insufficient resources and these singularly and in combination disastrously affect and compromise the ability of teachers in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria to effectively provide quality childhood care and education to the members of the Nigerian society.

Because the guiding philosophy and operational paradigms upon which private investors in education generally and early childhood care and education in particular operate is one that is deep rooted in profit maximization and exploitative cut throat capitalism (Nwaokugha & Nwogu, 2024: 70), these investors do not deem it necessary to provide infrastructure before contemplating opening such schools, rather such schools according to Nwaokugha (2015:78).

Characteristically exist in dilapidated structures, are usually operated in building not purposefully built for the purposes of school infrastructure and not licensed by the government as a school hence they exist secretly and illegally. In practical terms, those schools which exist in huts, warehouses and in residential houses in towns, urban centres and villages across Nigeria readily come to mind here and they disastrously lack the serenity and intellectual spirit expected of schools.

Also guided by profit maximization, investors in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria hardly see the benefits of recruiting or employing the right calibre of teachers, rather such profit minded investors employ mainly non specialist teachers. This practice has made some scholars to note that early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria has become safe haven for the employment of unqualified and under-qualified teachers, a development which Nwaokugha (2015:79) highlights when he writes that-

What obtains is that anyone who aspires to teach is employed by the management or proprietor and most private schools (early childhood care and education centres) in this category have become goldmines and employment destinations for candidates who claim they attended universities or any post-secondary educational institution but never had certificates. In some cases, holders of questionable secondary school certificates are employed as teachers.

Working at a level of education where the above presentation is the norm especially when the government does not show interests or does not recognize the contributions of that tier of education to the cognitive, social and emotional growth and development of members of the state and developments in the same tier of education are further compounded by being populated and dominated by quacks, can trigger and produce cumulative effects on the teachers, namely the depletion and demotivation of the few who are qualified, committed and dedicated to their duties. This development in early childhood care and education in Nigeria has made this level of education one where teachers leave in their large numbers on a daily basis due to lack of support and the undervaluing of their contributions to human development and the few who remain over stretch their ability and carrying capacity so much that they easily suffer burnt out, stress and other health challenges that negatively affect their personality. The established case of lack

of support, respect and the under-valuation of teachers in early childhood care and education institutions according to Kim, Brand and Zeltzer (2024) contributes to low job satisfaction and high turnover rate especially when teaching in early childhood care and education institutions is over demanding in terms of managing children who come from different backgrounds and working in an environment without the right infrastructure that can stimulate the intellectual curiosity and creativity of both the teachers and the learners.

Because learners in early childhood care and education institutions come from different socio-economic backgrounds, there is a higher tendency and possibility that the learners may manifest difficult and not-too-good behaviours that are capable of pushing their teachers into compromising their autonomy. In fact, in the face of those burn out, stress and other psychological imbalances that are sure variables with teachers in early childhood care and education institutions, these teachers compromise their autonomy and this is in addition to developing certain complexes that manifest in the inability of the early childhood care and education teachers to politely manage the situation, which easily generates additional problems for the teachers in the form of developing unnecessary enmity among themselves, that impair and stain their already established relationships.

It has also been established that the age level of learners that early childhood care and education teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions handle is another source of challenge that such teachers face. This is because the members of the public extend their lack of respect and regard for children to those who teach them, developments that manifest in lack of appreciation of the work of the teachers and because of the inability of the public and the state to appreciate teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions, these teachers develop psychological and inferiority complex. Part of where the psychological and inferiority complex originates from is the perception from members of the public that all teachers in early childhood care and education institutions are people who are not skilled and correspondingly have lost touch with real things of values in the society. In fact, the impression in some quarters of the society is that teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions do not have any meaning and tangible contributions to make for the advancement of humanity and this ill-conceived mindset of some members of the society affect early childhood care and education teachers very badly.

Another major challenge that teacher who teach in early childhood care and education institutions face is that as a segment of education that is the exclusive reserve of the private investors to provide, teachers in these institutions are the least to be considered for professional development programmes or opportunities. What this reveals is that professional development in terms of equipping early childhood care and education teachers with the capacity to improve themselves academically or acquire the latest classroom management skills, latest innovations in teaching and school community relations are distant dreams for early childhood care and education teachers. The near to nothing or total absence of these means that the professional growth of the teacher will continue to maintain a downward trend, the quality of their products will continue to depreciate and their contributions to national development may not be at par with the expectations of the society.

CONCLUSION

States that have hit the ground rolling in terms of development in all its configurations and ramifications are those states that make and continue to make substantial investments in human capital development and human capacity building and in recent times, there is a general awareness and acknowledgement that this investment starts with initiating visionary outlooks into the future. Charting a roadmap for achieving a future that meets a people's collective dreams is a conscious futuristic endeavour that must be initiated by the adult members of the society and achieved through rigorous and quality investments in the younger ones who the adults members of the society must well position so as to achieve and actualize the age long vision of the adult members of the society. Investments in early childhood care and education have been found across the globe to be a sure foundation for bringing to fruition this noble vision.

Early childhood care and education is crucial in the developmental trajectories and aspirations of individuals and states as it provides the foundations that shape, influence and determine what happens to the individual and the state later in the future. Younger ones who pass through early childhood care and education institutions demonstrate more maturity in social, emotional, moral, hygienic and sophisticated cognitive readiness and preparedness to embrace the rigours of academic pursuits at the primary school levels than those who did not pass through early childhood care and education institutions, a development that produces multiplier effects as states that consciously invest in early childhood care and education reap the dividends in the form of smooth transition of their sons and daughters from one level of education to the other without wasting time on remedial education. The benefits of investing in early childhood care and education are not limited to the younger ones alone as adults are also beneficiaries. The availability of early childhood care and education institutions enables parents to continuously engage in productive and economic activities that boost their economies and those of the state.

Achieving all that is associated with early childhood care and education is one hundred percent dependent on the teacher who teach at this level of education as teachers lay all the foundations for shaping, influencing and determining the future of younger ones and by extension the future of humanity. It has been acknowledged that whatever success that is recorded in teaching and learning at any level of education is a credit to the commitment, resilience and dedication of the teacher. Be this as it may, teachers particularly at the early childhood care and education level in Nigeria go through terrible challenges and obstacles that singularly and in combination compromise the quality of care and education they provide to the members of the Nigerian society.

These challenges which teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria face derive from the fact that the private investors are the sole providers of early childhood care and education, a development that has made that tier of education to be synonymous with underfunding, poor infrastructural facilities, safe haven for unqualified and under-qualified workforce, lack of collaboration with interested stakeholders, lack of provisions for staff development with its concomitant potentials to trigger and promote inferiority complex as well as mass exit of the few qualified members of staff. It can be pointed out that these challenges exist in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria simply because the private investors who solely man that tier of education in Nigeria are more interested in profit maximization rather than look for ways of improving the situation and the Nigerian government on its part is not ready to kickstart human capital development and initiate social justice measures through early childhood care and education that can realistically translate into the empowerment of the individual members of the community or Nigerian state as well as bring to the barest minimum economic, social, environmental and political inequalities.

These challenges teachers who teach in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria face are surmountable, can be overcome and can be addressed through practical policy measures. The government of Nigeria should be involved in providing early childhood care and education and not continue to make its provision the exclusive reserve of the private investors. It can start or demonstrate its commitment to the sector through massive policy formulation, one of which can focus on issues of teachers for the sector. Showing commitment in this direction can be in the form of making early childhood care and education compulsory and mandatory for every learner in Nigeria. The inability of the Nigerian government to be involved in the provision of early childhood care and education and the non-challant attitudes of Nigerians towards early childhood care and education can be pointing in the direction that Nigeria's education system does not have a foundation or more politely Nigeria's education system starts in the middle and as a provision without foundation, it is destined not to produce the expected dividends for the individual and the Nigerian state. In fact, it is a living example of the proverbial saying – building castles in the air. To start with, the government of Nigeria should establish units at the local government, state and federal levels that should be in-charge of early childhood care and education in the country.

Urgent steps should be taken to address teacher quality and infrastructural facility issues in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria and this can be done through mandating faculties of education in tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria to mount or establish departments of early

childhood care and education for the education of specialist teachers for that tier of education. On issues of infrastructure, the early childhood care and education units at the local government, state and federal levels must ensure compliance with regulating and controlling the operators and operations of pre-primary education where major emphasis must be on the availability of infrastructure and sustenance of minimum standards. The government must ensure that personnel who are to head these units must be people who may not compromise their moral integrity in the face of bribery and corruption that has caused epical, monumental and phenomenal damage to education in Nigeria. There should be special and enhanced pay for teachers who teach at this tier of education in Nigeria. Sufficient awareness should be created on the importance of providing early childhood care and education to learners and only candidates who have the natural dispositions and inclinations to work at this tier of education should be admitted into early childhood care and education departments in tertiary educational institutions so that they can be later employed. The era of employing any and any person to teach in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria should be jettisoned or rejected.

There should be collaboration between the federal, state and local governments and private investors on issues concerning early childhood care and education and this can be in the form of giving the private investors the free hand to introduce those competitive and innovative dynamics they are known for in their various investments in early childhood care and education institutions in matters of instruction, curriculum and pedagogy. To this end, the government can jettison or repudiate the idea of one size fits all provisions in early childhood care and education but should be environmentally sensitive and culturally responsive to the needs and peculiarities of the different learners and the different environments the different learners come from.

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